

Report on the UVP6 integration in gliders

Catalano, Picheral

Camille.catalano@imev-mer.fr, Marc.picheral@imev-mer.fr

2025/11/20

Contents

1	Context	2
2	UVP6 piloting and communication options.....	2
2.1	AUTO mode	2
2.2	SUPERVISED mode.....	3
2.3	Data integration	3
3	SeaGlider integration.....	3
3.1	Mechanical integration in SeaGlider	3
3.1.1	First CSCS integration	3
3.1.2	Akvaplan integration (2024).....	4
3.1.3	CSCS 2025 integration	5
3.2	Software integration in SeaGlider	6
3.2.1	The SeaGlider “sensor” mode	6
3.2.2	The SeaGlider “logger” mode.....	6
3.2.3	The SIRMA board.....	6
3.3	Conclusion for SeaGlider integration	7
4	Slocum integration	7
4.1	Mechanical integration in Slocum.....	8
4.2	Software integration in Slocum.....	9

4.3	Report on Slocum integration at GEOMAR (Christian Begler)	9
4.4	Conclusion for Slocum integration	10
5	SeaExplorer integration.....	10
5.1	Mechanical integration in SeaExplorer	10
5.2	Software integration in SeaExplorer	11
5.3	Conclusion for SeaExplorer integration.....	11
6	UVP6-Glider data management	11
7	Perspectives.....	11

1 Context

The UVP6 has currently been deployed on two gliders (SeaExplorer and SeaGlider), as well as the Slocum G2 and G3 vectors. This report details 1) the knowledge gained from the various UVP6-glider integrations, 2) what has already been achieved and how, and 3) explores further possibilities and available options for future integrations. Current knowledge of each gliders' technical features and capacities is also presented, including useful guidance for both using the UVP6 on existing gliders and for selecting gliders for UVP6 integration. The document synthesises the LOV knowledge and the report from a recent (2023/09/20) meeting at CSCS with Ehsan Abidi and Loizos Groutas.

We first briefly detail the communication possibilities of the UVP6 in the context of a glider integration. This information is organised in chapters per glider.

2 UVP6 piloting and communication options

It is useful to recall that all UVP6 raw data and images are internally recorded in the sensor and are only downloaded after the mission. It is also important to note that the power consumption of the UVP6LP (Low Power version) is maximum 0.8W at an acquisition rate of 1.3Hz, an expenditure which can be adjusted by changing the frequency. This change is done by selecting a proper preset configuration table (out of 10 available tables) in the instrument memory. As an example, the instrument drains only 0.1W at 0.1Hz.

The instrument is capable of providing in real time the abundance of particles sorted in 18 classes (size spectra) and the mean grey levels (capacity to reflect the red light of the sensor) of the same classes.

The UVP6LP can also provide the total abundance of particles (dominated by the smaller ones) as a 0-5 vdc signal on its analogue output. This option needs to be factory activated by the Hydroptic company before delivery.

An anticipated firmware, already used on profiling floats, permits the classification of objects in up to forty different classes, even if the actual classification model provides only twenty classes.

There are two applicable ways to interface with a UVP6 on a glider: the AUTO and the SUPERVISED UVP6 configuration modes.

2.1 AUTO mode

The first and simplest way is to use the AUTO mode of the UVP6. In this mode, the instrument starts acquisition using a unique preset configuration when powered ON and stops when power is removed.

It transmits the size spectra on its RS232 output (this can be deactivated to save a small amount of power) and, optionally, the total concentration on its analogue output. The classification information can also be transmitted on the same RS232 output.

In that piloting mode, the UVP6 acquires the images at a unique preset frequency for all dives and all depths. It can be controlled just through power.

2.2 SUPERVISED mode

In this mode, the glider powers the instrument ON and OFF but can also send commands to the UVP6 to start acquisition by selecting a proper preset configuration. This command can also provide the vector GPS time to the UVP6, allowing a perfect synchronisation of the glider and UVP6 data. Like the AUTO mode, the instrument sends data over its RS223 and analogue (option) outputs.

In this piloting mode, the UVP6 can be set to acquire and process data with different configurations according to profiles or depths, changing the image and/or black frequency, which can better optimise the power consumption of the instrument.

2.3 Data integration

The RS232 size spectra provided for each image (or blocs of a few images) cannot be transmitted to shore by the glider as this would require too much bandwidth. In order to optimise transmission, a per-depth-slice aggregation of the UVP6 data should be implemented. Real-time aggregated data is a real advantage as it allows more useful data to be obtained from the glider when it surfaces. This is also the only solution for transmitting the results of the optional embedded classification of images performed by the UVP6 (see below).

This aggregation of data is done by the NKE CTS5 profiling float as the vector is never recovered. LOV can provide the specifications for the implementation of this computing on demand.

3 SeaGlider integration

The SeaGlider vector was designed by the [University of Washington Applied Physics Lab](#) (APL). It has been licensed to different companies and is no longer produced by the APL except on demand. The SeaGlider is known (and was optimised) for its long endurance. Cyprus Subsea Consulting & Services (CSCS) recently acquired all spare parts for the SeaGlider and provides service for it. The APL is apparently not interested in UVP6 integration as they use their gliders primarily for physics, benefitting from the long range possibilities of the vector.

There are two versions of the instrument. The first makes up to 10% of the production and has a pink body. It was used for the first UVP6 trials during the BRIDGES project, with the UVP6 attached on its back. CSCS is convinced that this version of the integration and the glider itself are not adapted for the UVP6.

The second version represents 90% of the SeaGlider fleet and has a yellow body. CSCS integrated the UVP6 in an AKVAPLAN unit and deployed it at sea for two “Polar Front” studies off Norway in 2022 and 2023.

3.1 Mechanical integration in SeaGlider

3.1.1 First CSCS integration

Because of the additional weight of the UVP6 (1.6Kg in water) placed in the nose of the vector, the addition of flotation foam was needed. The experimental solution was to extend the UVP6-heavy nose using an extension cylinder, allowing the placement of 1000m rated foam inside the nose. This solution

was tested at sea and the glider could fly, although it was not well ballasted and the flying was not stable. CSCS thinks that the actual mounting can work with a good onsite ballasting prior to deployment.

The solution discussed by LOV and CSCS is to build a completely new and lighter nose with essentially the same shape as the original but without the integrated weight in the nose. This would permit much less foam to be used than with the tested configuration. This nose could also be built with more exotic fibres like carbon to make it much lighter and reduce its volume and compressibility. The use of a more efficient (i.e., less compressible) foam should also be envisaged.

There is no plan today either at CSCS or at LOV to develop and test such a nose, as there is no operational SeaGlider in the French scientific community. We have not contacted Akvaplan about their projects on this vehicle.

The cable from the UVP6 to the SeaGlider cannot be a standard delivery from Hydroptic.

Seaglider equipped with the UVP6 and the extension tube.

3.1.2 Akvaplan integration (2024)

The Akvaplan team applied the recommendations issued from the first integration by CSCS.

Seaglider equipped with the UVP6 and without any extension tube.

Below is the report from Ehsan Abdi who did this second integration: *We had a very short mission (2.5 days). After some initial compass calibration and trimming, glider flight seemed pretty good. However, since we were in a very strong Norwegian coastal current and so it was not possible to assess the impact of the UVP6 on the speed of the glider. Overall, the main aim of this mission for us was to test the flight with the new design and we are quite happy with that. We are planning to deploy the glider again later in fall. The glider deepest dive was down to 700m.*

The technical solution seems to perform well and some new dives will be performed late 2024 by Akvaplan.

3.1.3 CSCS 2025 integration

Report from Ehsan Abdi (eab@akvaplan.niva.no):

CSCS for some reason decided to do it their own way. The important part is that similar to our design, they also removed the nose weight from their glider which is the key, but instead of using our bracket method, decided to recreate the UVP6 arm on the glider. You can see a photo of this attached. It works but I think this is unnecessary, since using the original arm has many benefits over doing it this way and it's just much simpler. Also, I noticed some major corrosion around the bolts which I suspect is due to the poor-quality anodization of the aluminium bracket and/or lack of Tefgel or other isolation methods.

Regarding the flight, our glider (AKVAPLAN) had a better overall performance as you can see from the track attached. We managed to go beyond the shelf break and dive all the way down to 1000m with both EK80 and UVP6 recording the whole way. Whereas their glider struggled more with the currents. This was due to better ballasting of the glider, leaving us more room for thrust. However, surprisingly the orientation they chose worked better when you take a closer look at an individual dive. This seems counter intuitive because at first glance a top-heavy orientation seems result in less stability but what I realized in this mission was that when you have the UVP6 in horizontal orientation, it acts more like a wing and therefore creates uneven lift forces. This results in glider oscillations. Whereas a vertical orientation acts more like a rudder and therefore results in a more stable flight. This is very easy to fix in our design, and we just need to rotate the fairing 90 degrees before re-attaching it. I am also planning to create a cover piece like in Alseamar latest solution for the next deployment.

3.2 Software integration in SeaGlider

The SeaGlider firmware is quite open and makes the addition of a new sensor feasible. There are two ways to set up a sensor.

3.2.1 The SeaGlider “sensor” mode

The first way is the “sensor” mode. The glider turns the sensor ON and OFF and monitors its output, similar to any analogue sensor. This integration of the UVP6 is trivial even if not tested. The onshore user can check that the UVP6 is functioning thanks to the analogue output voltage recording which provides total particle data. The UVP6 power is constant over depth and profiles and depends on the preset configuration in AUTO mode.

3.2.2 The SeaGlider “logger” mode

The second way is very similar but does not permit the instrument to record and send data without a specific interface board.

Without this board, the glider uses the “logger” procedure to send commands (user configurable) to the UVP6 after powering the sensor. The configuration cannot be changed during a profile according to depth and the acquisition frequency therefore remains constant. The “logger” mode cannot record data. No real time data can be transmitted in this mode unless the analogue output of the sensor is connected to a “sensor” input. This configuration has not been checked and appears useless as it does not provide significant additional possibilities compared to the “sensor” mode.

3.2.3 The SIRMA board

CSCS developed the SIRMA board which can be moulded to a waterproof external cable called the SmartCable. This configuration has not yet been tested; the only solution nowadays is to set the board in a waterproof housing.

The SIRMA board is a very low power configurable system programmed in C++. The board design and the firmware are provided on [GitHub](#). CSCS can place the board inside the Akvaplan SeaGlider housing and use the glider “logger” mode to send commands (including glider depth and time) to the SIRMA

which itself pilots the UVP6 in a smart way. It allows the definition of per-depth acquisition settings and the recovery of synthesised UVP6 data to send from the surface to shore. The main interest of this configuration is its allowance of different per-depth acquisition rates and the transmission of per-depth-slice synthesised UVP6 size spectrum and classification results. The drawback of this configuration is its need to be connected to the SIRMA board to change the depth configurations using a compiled software rather than a user-friendly menu or GUI. The other disadvantage is the need to place the board in the glider. This could be mitigated by further integration of the board with the UVP6, which would allow remote programming without physically activating a pin on the board. The UVP6 would be set in SUPERVISED mode, with the SIRMA board allowing ten different configurations.

The CSCS SIRMA solution was tested and validated during the August 2023 PolarFront cruise. The UVP6 acquired data at different rates according to depth and the synthesised size spectra were sent to shore. The trueness of the cruise data has not been yet tested by CSCS or LOV (due to some modifications in the netcdf files from the glider).

The SIRMA boards.

Connexion diagram successfully tested on SeaGlider

3.3 Conclusion for SeaGlider integration

There are currently two options which seem functional. The first, and simplest, is using the ON/OFF switch, the analogue output, and the AUTO mode. The acquisition rate would remain constant over depth which does not allow fine power management but homogenises the sampling rate and the object detection probabilities. Acquisition parameters could be set by any SeaGlider user provided that a mechanical kit is made available and the UVP6-LP analogue output is activated in the factory. The second option using the SIRMA cable is much more reactive but not yet available outside of CSCS.

4 Slocum integration

The Teledyne company manufacturing the Slocum gliders has been contacted twice in the past few years, first by LOV and again by the Bioglider consortium. Teledyne see no interest in having the UVP6 as an on-the-shelf sensor for their vehicle and are not supportive.

The National Oceanographic Centre (NOC) in Southampton recently recruited an expert from Teledyne and will soon provide services to the users of Slocum gliders, which may open new possibilities.

4.1 Mechanical integration in Slocum

There are two versions actively in service, the older G2 and the more recent G3. There are deep and shallow options on both, as well as different body configurations. There is no standard flooded nose, allowing easy integration of the UVP6 on any version.

The CNRS supervised the design and prototyping of two mounting kits for Slocum G2 and G3. The kit was designed in order to have a fully ballasted nose (i.e. the foam compensates the kit and UVP6 combined weights), and in order to preserve and to keep the possibility of laying the glider on its original trolley without any appendices underneath. One of these kits was mounted and field tested by CSCS on the Bergen University Slocum G3 glider. This glider was not extensively deployed. The second kit was provided to Geomar and utilised during a cruise on a Slocum G2. The foam-light interface of the second kit broke at sea, interrupting the deployment. The Geomar team noticed a much lower flying speed of the glider and a need for the rudder to compensate for the drag of the UVP6 kit in the front of the glider.

Thanks to the remarks issued from the mounting of the kit by CSCS and Geomar, a second kit has been prototyped with Hydroptic to fix some of the critical fragility and mounting problems. This kit can be set either horizontally or rotated vertically to keep the glider on its track, obviating the rudder corrections.

This new kit has been mounted for testing on a G2 and only needs a final mounting test on a G3 (which should not be a problem) before being made commercially available from Hydroptic.

The cable from the UVP6 to the Slocum cannot be a standard delivery from Hydroptic, as there are too many possible configurations of the connectors and their positions on the glider. It will therefore be made based on the glider owners' requirements.

The SLOCUM G3 equipped with the first version of the UVP6 kit.

The SLOCUM G2 deep equipped with the Hydroptic version of the UVP6 kit. The glider nose has been removed.

4.2 Software integration in Slocum

If utilised in AUTO mode and only with the recording of its analogue output, the UVP6 can easily be interfaced with any Slocum provided that a kit is available and a proper cable moulded. Geomar tested this option on its G2 (without recording the analogue output). Their configuration should be shared.

The possibility of implementing a smarter solution relies on the backseat driver available on the G3 glider only (NOC will probably also be able to provide it on the G2 as well). This solution also implies the use of a SIRMA board which will be programmed differently than on the SeaGlider but provide exactly the same possibilities. The board will in this case mimic another “known” sensor to the glider. The pros and cons. are the same for both gliders, as well as for the positioning of the board. CSCS set a SIRMA board inside the Norwegian Slocum G3, associated with the first prototype of the mounting kit. For the Slocum, as for the SeaGlider, the functionalities were set so as to allow their shore station to get per-depth-slice size spectra of particles from the UVP6.

Connexion diagram successfully tested on SeaGlider G3 (CSCS)

Connexion diagram successfully tested on SeaGlider G2 (GEOMAR)

4.3 Report on Slocum integration at GEOMAR (Christian Begler)

To run the UVP6 on a Slocum glider I had to use a glider with an external connector at the stiffener ring of the science bay. These gliders are usually prepared to carry external instruments like Rockland Scientific Microrider MR1000 or a Seabird SUNA Nitrate sensor.

The "datalogger"-proglet of the Slocum Science Firmware allows to power a connected sensor simply ON and OFF. The datalogger proglet has to be configured with the correct power bit in the file "proglets.dat" of the science bay controller. A science bay prepared for Microrider can provide only limited current to its power bit, due to a resistor. That doesn't allow running a UVP6.

Instead I used a science bay for SUNA. Since a SUNA draws up to 700mA currents this board is also well suited for the UVP6 (I assume peaks to 400mA for the UVP6 at 14V). The cable MCIL8M-MCIL8F Glider-SUNA could be used as well, but the internal connector from the MCBH8F bulkhead to the science board had to be re-wired to match the pin-requirements of the UVP6.

The analogue output of the UVP6 wasn't used, data integration should be done with TWR.

The light and camera mounted to the sides of the Slocum increased the cross section of the glider by 40%. The resulting slower speed had a significant impact on the glider's flight performance.

4.4 Conclusion for Slocum integration

Hydroptic will soon be able to provide a commercial kit, which will allow any user to set a UVP6 on a Slocum G2 or G3 glider. This kit apparently has a strong impact on the flying capabilities and thus the endurance of the glider. It can be positioned in two ways but has not been tested vertically.

The simple piloting powered in AUTO mode was proven to work even if the analogue data were not recorded nor transmitted. Similar to the SeaGlider, the SIRMA cable associated with the SUPERVISED mode is a smart solution but is currently unavailable outside of CSCS.

5 SeaExplorer integration

The Alseamar company provides the only on-the-shelf solution for the UVP6. This solution has been proven to be reliable, as more than 6000 dives have been performed to date. LOV partially funded the integration (mechanical and software) and made most of the dives using two gliders. Scientists from the Canary Islands, Vietnam and Israel have also purchased the system and operated SeaExplorers with UVP6s. There is therefore a minimum of 5 operational gliders equipped with the UVP6.

5.1 Mechanical integration in SeaExplorer

Alseamar equips their glider with a strong kit which requires the use of an RBR Legato CTD probe instead of the pumped SeaBird one.

CNRS personnel reported an impact (not yet evaluated) of the UVP6 on glider performance, which did not however prevent its use in frontal zones, both in the Ligurian current and in the Atlantic front between eddies during the APERO cruise.

The SeaExplorer equipped with the UVP6.

Alseamar is now (2024) proposing an optimised fitting which reduces the drag of the UVP6 and improves the flying capability.

The SeaExplorer with its new UVP6 fitting.

5.2 Software integration in SeaExplorer

Alseamar implemented drivers permitting per-depth settings, enabling the optimisation of the sampling frequency according to depth. The drivers allow a re-programming from shore when the glider surfaces, as well as the transmission of a subset of the data to the piloting and data Glimpse application. The data transmitted is the counts of the seven first slides every 30 seconds. This data allows some operational control over the UVP6, as well as quality validation of the recorded information. The driver and the Glimpse application do not yet permit the per-depth-slice aggregation of the data, nor the transmission of the taxonomic classification of the images by the UVP6.

Connexion diagram successfully tested on SeaExplorer

5.3 Conclusion for SeaExplorer integration

This configuration is the only on-the-shelf solution today. It has been proven to be fully operational by end users and has already provided substantial scientific data.

6 UVP6-Glider data management

The data and images recovered from the UVP6 deployed on gliders can be made publicly available thanks to the EcoPART/EcoTAXA web applications.

LOV developed a Matlab code which creates samples and automatizes the synchronisation of the glider positioning and sensor data with the UVP6 data prior to importation (instead of having to do it manually in the UVPapp application). This code is open on GitHub and can be modified/improved upon by users. It works on SeaExplorer data thanks to the fixed output format from the glider. It also works on the SeaGlider data from the PolarFront experiment but seems sensible to changes in the netcdf files from the glider.

7 Perspectives

Some presented configurations have not been tested and are summarised in the figures below. They may work both on SeaGlider and SLOCUM gliders provided that some tests and software developments are carried out on the SIRMA solution.

Three possible configurations for SeaGlider and Slocum gliders.

Apart from the finalisation of the SeaGlider and Slocum integrations, it would be great if all gliders could provide (specification document available from LOV) per-depth-slice aggregated size spectra (plus taxonomy) to their base stations (application) and that these stations could synthesise these data in standardised netcdf files compatible with the CORIOLIS system and the EcoPART portal. LOV will soon be capable of specifying these files.

A new (already in use on CTS5 profiling floats) firmware version of the UVP6 will perform an embedded classification of the images and transmit the results via the RS232 link. This functionality will be useful for specific missions. The SIRMA cable may be a useful solution for that purpose even if further developments are needed. LOV will start discussions with Alseamar for the per-depth-slice aggregation of the transmitted data, including the results of the classification.